

EFFECTS OF ELEMENTS OF WATER SUPPLY IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGY IN SOYA IRRIGATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF BUKHARA REGION

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Abstract: *This article provides information about the work being done by the state to grow soybeans in Uzbekistan, the conditions created. There is also brief information about the natural conditions of Bukhara region, its location, water sources, drainage networks. At the same time, in this article, mainly on the experiments carried out on the middle-ripening "Nafis" and middle-ripening "Uzbek-6" varieties of soybeans in the Bukhara region, the elements of water-repellent irrigation technology in irrigation The results of experiments on the effects of*

Keywords: *shade, irrigation, technology, soil, moisture, delta, blue mass, egat, hydrogel, straw, field, flowering, biology, agrotechnics, black film.*

ВЛИЯНИЕ ЭЛЕМЕНТОВ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ВОДОСНАБЖЕНИЯ ПРИ ОРОШЕНИИ СОИ В УСЛОВИЯХ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

Аннотация: *В данной статье представлена информация о проводимой государством работе по выращиванию сои в Узбекистане, созданных условиях. Также даны краткие сведения о природных условиях Бухарской области, ее расположении, источниках воды, дренажных сетях. При этом в данной статье, в основном на опытах, проведенных на среднеспелых сортах сои «Нафис» и среднеспелых «Узбек-6» в условиях Бухарской области, рассмотрены элементы водоотталкивающей технологии полива при поливе. Результаты опытов по воздействию*

Ключевые слова: *тен, полив, технология, почва, влага, дельта, синяя масса, эгат, гидрогел, солома, поле, свечение, биология, агротехника, черная пленка.*

BUXORO VILOYATI SHAROITIDA SOYANI SUG'ORISHDA SUV TEJOVCHI SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI ELEMENTLARINING SUG'ORISH OLDI TUPROQ NAMLIGIGA TA'SIRI

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada soya o'simligini O'zbekistonda yetishtirish*

bo'yicha davlatimiz tomonidan olib borilayotgan ishlar, yaratib berilayotgan sharoitlar haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Buxoro viloyatining tabiiy sharoitlari, joylashuv o'rni, suv manbaalari, zax qochirish tarmoqlari haqida ham qisqacha ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Shu bilan birga ushbu maqolada asosan Buxoro viloyati sharoitida soya o'simligining o'rtapishar "Nafis" va o'rtapishar "O'zbek-6" navi ustida olib borilgan tajribalar sug'orishda yusuvtejoyvchi sug'orish texnologiyasi yelementlarining sug'orish oldi tuproq namligiga ta'siri bo'yicha olib borilgan tajribalar natijalari haqida yozilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *soya, sug'orish, texnologiya, tuproq, namlik, delta, ko'k massa, yegat, gidrogel, somon, dala, gullash, biologiya, agtotexnika, qora plyonka.*

Today, a lot of attention is paid to agriculture. In the world's soybean-growing countries, it is important to increase its productivity, increase the quality of crop production, increase productivity through timely agro-technical measures and the use of land use technologies, mineral fertilizers for high-yielding varieties. depending on the number and duration of the tabs. Properly determining the norms, number and timing of shade irrigation, taking into account soil and climatic conditions, will have a positive impact on the quantity and quality of crops. Therefore, scientific research is being conducted to grow high-quality and high-yield soybeans.

Great attention is paid to agriculture in the country, the use of modern irrigation methods in the cultivation of crops, ie the use of water-saving irrigation technologies, achieving an yefficient and high-quality increase in productivity while saving water. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" makes a significant contribution to the further development of agriculture. It is also included in the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947. That is, the priorities of yeconomic development and liberalization are highlighted in Section 3.3 on the modernization and accelerated development of agriculture. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-3144 of July 24, 2017 Resolution No. PP-2832 and amendments to this resolution "On the creation of high-yielding soybean varieties in the Republic for 2017-2021, the yestablishment of primary seed production, cultivation and yexpansion of the area The resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 11, 2020 "On the introduction of water-saving technologies in agriculture" PQ – 4919 risida on measures for accelerated organization [8].

In the meadows of Bukhara region - alluvial, saline and saline soils, medium-ripening shade varieties "Nafis" and late-ripening Uzbek-6 varieties are yelements of water-saving irrigation technology in the order of 70-70-60% of the ChDNS. Field yexperiments In 2017-2019, field research was conducted on the soils of medium mechanical composition of the farm "Abror Muhammad Sakhovati" located in the territory of Halvagaron Farm, Vobkent district, Bukhara

region.

Briefly about the natural location of Bukhara region, where the experiments were carried out, Bukhara region is located in the south-western part of the Republic, occupying the area of 640-690 northern and 380-440 western latitudes. The land area is 39,400 km². The Bukhara oasis is located in the central part of the Kyzylkum desert, bordering Kashkadarya region in the southeast, Turkmenistan in the northwest, Khorezm region and the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the northeast, and Navoi region in the northwest. It is located in the lower and middle parts of the dried-up riverbed, and the main part of its land area consists of barren pastures. The Bukhara oasis is located between two major deserts in the natural geographical location of the Republic: between the Kyzylkum and Karakum deserts of Central Asia.

Irrigated lands are located in the plains of the Southern Kyzylkum desert. The Bukhara oasis stretches along the banks of the Zarafshan River to the Bukhara and Karakol oases.

Bukhara-Karakul oasis Irrigated lands in the ancient and modern delta of the Zarafshan river and its surrounding areas, Bukhara and Karakul, Karmana-Konimex settings are coming. Karmana-Konimex oasis is located in the foothills of the upper reaches of the Zarafshan River, and the Zarafshan River serves as a channel for groundwater; Bukhara region is located in the central part of the basin and forms the sub-aerial delta of the Zarafshan River. The relief of the desert on the left bank of the oasis, which surrounds the left bank of the oasis, is surrounded by ancient erosion pits, such as Khoja-Kab, Lower-Tomb, Kunja-Lake. The first depth will be used as a reservoir to collect water from the Zarafshan River and the Amu-Bukhara canal.

The Karakol oasis is located in the lower delta of the river and at low hypsometric heights. The Karmana-Konimex oasis is located between the Nurata Mountains in the north and the Zirabulak Mountains in the south. The Karakol oasis is bordered by the Bukhara oasis by the Kyzylkum plateau.

The area of Bukhara region is 4 million 200 thousand hectares, irrigated lands - 275100 hectares, of which 21329 hectares (0.3%) are gardens, 2674186 hectares (64%) are pastures, 205616 hectares (4.9%) are forests and 978,348 hectares (23.3%) are other lands, the remaining 7.5% are abandoned lands.

Regarding the biological classification of soybean varieties studied in the experimental fields:

Biological classification of soybean variety "Nafis": Biological classification of soybean variety "Nafis" Authors: Saitkanova RU, Sadikova NI, Ibragimov F.Yu., Sattarov MA, Mirzaeva I. Created by individual selection method at the Uzbek Agricultural Research Institute . Botanical species - *Glycine hispida* L. Growth period 115-120 days. Plant height 145-150 cm. The number of lower pods is – 120–130, and the number of grains per pod is 2–4. The weight of 1000 soybean seeds is 165-175 g. The grain contains 40-41% protein and 25-27% fat. Resistant to spills, diseases and mechanized harvesting. Nafis soybean can yield 30-32 s / ha of grain and 250-300 s / ha of green mass under favorable conditions.

Biological classification of Uzbek – 6 varieties of soybeans: Biological classification of medium Uzbek – 6 varieties of soybeans Authors: Saltas MM, Bugina O.V., Yunusov B.K. Created by the Uzbek Research Institute of Rice. Botanical species - Glycine hispida L. Growth period 140-145 days. Plant height 160-170 cm. The lower pods are 12-14 cm long, the number of horns is 3-5, the number of pods per plant is 150-160, and the number of grains per pod is 2-4. 1000 seeds weigh 160-170 g. The protein content of grain is 41-42%. Stem contains 22-24% protein and 21-22% fat. Intended for bed rest, shedding, disease resistance and mechanized harvesting. Under favorable conditions, the variety can yield 32-35 s / ha of grain and 400-450 s / ha of green mass.

Field experiments were carried out in the following system to identify elements of the scientifically based water-based irrigation technology of the above-mentioned shade varieties (see Table 1).

According to the experimental system, field experiments were carried out in 10 variants and 3 returns. The dimensions of the sections are as follows: length of the yedge $L_e = 100$ m, distance between the yedges 0.6 m, number of rows 8, of which 4 are calculated rows, the rest are protective rows, in which case the area of one variant

$8 \times 0,6 \times 100 = 480$ m², a reduction area $480 \times 10 = 4800$ m², total experimental area $4800 \times 3 = 1.44$ ha and experimental system diagram..

1 - table.

Experimental system

Variant	Irrigation methodi	Yegat length, m	Yegat spacing cm	Water consumption per hectare, l / s
"Nafis" variety				
1	Irrigation (control)	100	60	0,20; 0,14; 0,08
2	Irrigate the area with a black film			
3	Irrigate the soil with hydrogel after planting			
4	Straw watering between rows			
5	Irrigation of the opposite side			
"O'zbek-6" variety				
6	Irrigation (control)	100	60	0,20; 0,14; 0,08
7	Irrigate the area with a black film			
8	Irrigate the soil with hydrogel after planting			
9	Straw watering between rows			
10	Irrigation of the opposite side			

Before dwelling on the effect of elements of aquifer irrigation technology on pre-irrigation soil moisture in soybean irrigation, the limited field moisture capacity of the experimental field soil is given by the norm of water plant growth, development, harvesting and vertical growth of the plant. This is very important in the care of the plant. Given that water is involved in all the chemical and biochemical processes that take place in plants, it is also a major source of organic matter in plants. One of the water-physical parameters of irrigated lands is the limited field moisture capacity, which allows to plan the amount of water supplied to plants.

The limited field moisture capacity of the soil plays an important role in determining the norms and timing of irrigation and in meeting the water needs of crops. Therefore, it is important to determine the limited field moisture capacity of the soil based on the soil climatic conditions of each region (see Table 2).

The ratio of soil to limited field moisture capacity (ChDNS) was determined prior to field research.

It is known that many of our scientists Mirzajanov Q.M., Beshpalov N.F., Rijov S.N., Rakhimboev F.M., Khamidov M.H., Fayziev T.Z., Norkulov U., Avliyokulov N.Ye., Isashev A., Isaev S.H. and Matyakubov B.Sh. According to the research, in the harsh continental climate of Central Asia, the water-physical properties of the soil, the order of irrigation and its water consumption depending on the different hydromodular regions are widely covered in the scientific literature.

2 – table.

Limited field moisture capacity of soil, in%, (ChDNS)

Soil laers, cm	ChDNS relative to dry soil weight, %		
	2017 year	2018 year	2019 year
0-10	22,3	22,4	22,2
10-20	22,4	22,6	22,5
20-30	21,6	21,7	21,6
30-40	21,4	21,5	21,5
40-50	20,8	21,1	20,9
50-60	20,7	20,8	20,7
60-70	20,9	20,9	20,9
70-80	21,4	21,5	21,3
80-90	21,6	21,6	21,5
90-100	21,8	21,8	21,9
0-40	21,9	22,1	22,0
0-50	21,7	21,9	21,7
0-70	21,4	21,6	21,5
0-100	21,5	21,6	21,5

The data show that in the experimental area, the soil moisture content varied over the years relative to the limited field moisture capacity in the average one-meter laer. In different laers of the experimental field soil, the field moisture capacity varied from 20.7% to 23.4%, depending on the density of the laers. In 2017, the field moisture capacity was 21.9% in the 0–40 cm laer, 21.7% in the 0–50 cm laer and 21.5% in the 0–100 cm laer. . In 2018, the limited field moisture capacity of the soil was 22.1% in the 0–40 cm laer, 21.9% in the 0–50 cm laer, and 21.6% in the 0–100 cm laer. did. As a result of experimental observations in 2019, the limited field moisture capacity of the soil was 22.0% in the 0–40 cm laer, 21.7% in the 0–50 cm laer and 21.5% in the 0–100 cm laer. was found to be These values are typical for alluvial alluvial soils of the Bukhara oasis with average mechanical composition, according to the table.

Regarding the effect of elements of water-saving irrigation technology on pre-irrigation soil moisture in soybean irrigation: In variant 3, irrigation was carried out at 15.3% of the soil weight and 70.6% of the ChDNS in the flowering phase, and 16% of the soil weight at the flowering stage. 9%, compared to 70.6-70.9% compared to ChDNS. During the shade ripening period, irrigation was not carried out due to high soil moisture. During our observations, in the cultivation of shade, mulching between rows with straw, in the 4 – variant, the pre-irrigation soil moisture was 70-70-60% relative to the ChDNS, and irrigation in the flowering phase of the soil was carried out. Irrigation was carried out at 14.6% of the total area, 68.4% of the ChDNS, and 70.8-70.5% of the ChDNS during the flowering and fruiting phases. During the ripening period, irrigation was carried out at a soil moisture content of 67.1% relative to the ChDNS. Germination in the case of irrigation on the opposite side of the field, in the flowering phase of the shade when the soil moisture is 14.6% relative to ChDNS, in the flowering and fruiting phase 70.8–70 , Was carried out at 2%. In the shade ripening phase, irrigation was carried out at 60.2%. During the experiments, the results of irrigation of the late Uzbek-6 shade variety were similar to the above experiments.

Conclusion:

In the case of soybean irrigation, soil moisture was well maintained during irrigation in options 2 and 3, when the soil was irrigated mainly with a black film and the soil was irrigated with hydrogel. and 1 time less irrigation than our other options. Our experiment was observed in Option 1, which showed that soil moisture was lower than in other variants and that large amounts of water were used for irrigation.

REFERENCES LITERATURA

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 10, 2019 No PF-5853 "On approval of the Strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" (www.lex.uz) ;
2. Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 (www.lex.uz);
3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev dated March 14, 2017 "On measures to increase the sowing of soybeans and soybeans in the Republic in 2017-2021" No PP-2832 (www.lex.uz);
4. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev dated December 11, 2020 "On measures to further accelerate the introduction of water-saving technologies in agriculture" PQ – 4919 ((www.lex.uz);
5. Bupalov N.F. under the general editorship of the team of authors, // *Gidromodulnoe rayonirovanie i rejima orosheniya selskokhozyaystvennykh kultur po oblastyam Respubliki Uzbekistan* // Tashkent - 1992 yil;
6. Dospexov B.A. // *Methodology of field opyta*. Moscow: Agropromizdat, // 1985;
7. Sattorov M and others – Recommendation on "Technology of soybean

cultivation in Bukhara region", Tashkent-2017

8. Atabaeva H., Kadyrkhojaev - "Botany" - Tashkent - 2006;

9. J.Sh.Fazliyev., Sh.M.Tojiev., Sh.D.Khalikov. (2024). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 504–509. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/107>

10. I.J.Xudayev, I.J.Xudayev, & Sh.M.Tojiyev. (2024). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKLANLI EGATLARDAN G'O'ZANI SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 514–519. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/109>

11. Fazliyev, Z. S., Shokhimardonova, N. S., Sobirov, F. T., Ravshanov, U. K., & Baratov, S. S. (2014). Technology of the drip irrigation use in gardens and vineyards. *The Way of Science*, 56.

12. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). INTEGRATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 945–950. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/195>

13. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). TEXNIKA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI AXBOROT TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QITISHNING MUHIM YO'NALISHLARI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 938–944. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/194>

14. Fazliyev, J. (2017). Drip irrigation technology in gardens. *Интернаука. Science Journal*, 7(11).

15. Фазлиев, Ж.Ш.(2017).Боғларда томчилатиб суғориш технологияси. *Интернаука*,(7-3),71-73.

16. Ikrom, I. (2023). KASBIY TAYYORGARLIKNING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI BO'YICHA PEDAGOGIK TAJRIBA-SINOV ISHLARI NATIJALARINING TAHLILI. In *Uz-Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 626-633).

17. Shaxrilloevich, I. I. (2023). DIDACTIC CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF STUDENTS OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH. *Academia Repository*, 4(10), 142-145.

18. Саримсаков, М. М. (2023, May). СПОСОБЫ ПОЛИВА И УРОЖАЙНОСТЬ ИНТЕНСИВНЫХ ЯБЛОНЕВЫХ САДОВ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 14, pp. 173-175).

19. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш., & Шохимарданова, Н. Ш. (2024). БОҒЛАРНИ ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШДА ТУПРОҚ-ГРУНТ НАМЛАНИШ КОНТУРИНИ АНИҚЛАШ УСЛУБИ. *IMRAS*, 7(2), 34-38.

20. Sadirovich, S. N. (2022). The Significance of Problem Situation Assignments in Teaching the Science of Machine Details. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(8), 30-32.

21. Sattorovich, S. U., & Qobil o'g'li, S. F. (2022). BUG 'DOY O 'SIMLIGI VA DONINING XALQ XO 'JALIGIDA BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI.

22. Xamrayev Kamol, Sharifov Firdavs, & Yusupova Oynura. (2024). TUPROQ SHO'RINI YUVISHDA BIOSOLVENT BIRIKMASINI TUPROQ SUV-TUZ MUVOZANATIGA TA'SIRI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 458–460. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/97>

23. Khudaev, I. J., & Shoximardanova, N. S. (2023). FEATURES OF DRIP IRRIGATION OF CROPS. *PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS*, 2(24), 157-160.

24. Худаев, И. Ж., & Шохимарданова, Н. Ш. (2023). ҚОВУН ПОЛИЗ ЭКИНИНИНГ БИОЛОГИК ВА МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. In *Uz-Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 479-482).

25. Fazliyev, J. (2018). Modern irrigation methods for gardens. *Science*, 22, 24-26.